

CURE MONITORING OF AN AUTOCLAVE MANUFACTURED INDUSTRIAL PART: ADDED VALUE OF COMPLEMENTARY INSTRUMENTATION

F. Collombet^{1*}, G. Luyckx², C. Sonnenfeld³, Y-H. Grunevald⁴, Y. Davila¹, M. Torres¹, X. Jacob⁵, K-T. Wu⁶, S. Rodriguez⁵, B. Douchin¹, L. Crouzeix¹, R. Bazer-Bachi¹, T. Geernaert³, J. Degrieck², F. Berghmans³

¹ Université de Toulouse, INSA, UPS, Institut Clément Ader, 133 C Av. de Rangueil, F-31077 Toulouse.

² Universiteit Gent, Sint-Pietersnieuwstraat 41, B-9000 Gent.

³ Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Pleinlaan 2, B-1050 Brussel.

⁴ Composites, Expertise & Solutions, 4 Rue G. Vallerey, F-31320 Castanet Tolosan.

⁵ Laboratory of Human Being Physics Applied to the Environment, 118 Rte de Narbonne, F-31062 Toulouse.

⁶ Industrial Materials Institute, 75 Bd de Mortagne, Boucherville, Québec, J4B6Y4, Canada.

* Corresponding author (francis.collombet@iut-tlse3.fr)

Keywords: *Cure cycle monitoring, Residual strain, Fiber Bragg grating, Flexible Ultrasonic Transducers*

Abstract

This paper introduces part of the results of the project called “Instrumentation with Multi-sensor for Composite Materials and structures (I2MC)” supported by RTRA STAE foundation. The main goal of the paper is to show the complementarities of different monitoring devices such as flexible ultrasonic transducers (FUT), micro-structured (MOF), and DTG[®] optical fibers, in order to infer the initial state of the composite structure by determining the residual strains. The complementarities between FUT and optical fiber sensing are defined as follows. The FUT measurements cannot estimate the strain however can determine the time when the transfer between the composite material and the optical fiber is effective. The onset of the gelation and the corresponding transverse residual strains can be quantified by the MOF FBG. Combined with the measurements of DTGs[®] embedded in capillaries, to avoid the influence on the measurement of transverse residual strains, a complete overview of the induced residual strains can be obtained.

1 Introduction

The project called “Instrumentation with Multi-sensor for Composite Materials and structures (I2MC)” supported by RTRA STAE foundation (France) has gathered the expertise of research and

industrial teams to study in-core instrumentation of composites structures by applying the Multi-Instrumented Technological Evaluator toolbox (MITE toolbox) [1]. The overall objective of this study is to evaluate embedded sensors in a representative situation during the life cycle of a composite part.

As part of this collaboration, we have proposed a multi-instrumentation set-up for monitoring a composite structure during its curing phase. The specific objective is to showcase the complementarity of different embedded devices such as flexible ultrasonic transducers (FUTs) [2], micro-structured optical fibers (MOFs) based sensors [3] and draw tower gratings (DTG[®]s) fabricated in regular optical fibers, in order to infer the initial state of the composite structure by means of its residual strains.

A set of FUTs is placed by pairs on either side of the composite plate in order to follow the evolution of the material through its thickness. The ultrasonic measurements reveal the physical state of the composite plies during curing through viscoelastic properties evolution. The time of flight and the attenuation are analyzed. The curing phases are identified with a unique signature beginning with the mold/composite coupling, passing through resin reticulation and finishing with composite consolidation. At this stage, no real-time monitoring has been implemented, but this could be achieved by

using the same hardware. These first measurements, and the processing used here do not give local information, but a mean value through the sample thickness.

On one hand, in contrast to the method presented hereafter, the ultrasonic measurements cannot estimate the strain; however allow to monitor the beginning of the cure process. It indicates the time when the strain transfer between the composite material and the optical fibers is effectuated.

On the other hand, we report on the use of a particular type of MOFs to study the cure cycle of the composite. This MOF has been designed so as to feature a much larger sensitivity to transverse strain than conventional birefringent fibers. Furthermore, the MOF features a very low sensitivity of the phase modal birefringence to temperature.

The measurements with this specialty optical fiber are supported by the readings of DTG[®] surrounded by a capillary to isolate them from transverse effects in the composite material [4]. DTGs[®] are high-strength fiber Bragg gratings (FBGs) featuring low bending losses [5], which make them excellent candidates for cure cycle monitoring.

After introducing the different technologies used in this study, we elaborate on the complementarities of the different sensor technologies when used for cure cycle monitoring. We also provide an outlook on future research and applications opportunities.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 The monitored composite part in autoclave

The composite structure studied here is a M10/T300 carbon-epoxy plate of 175 x 640 mm with two drop-off zones as shown in Figure 1. The composite plate (called Double drop off evaluator) has three main zones of different thicknesses. First, the central zone is the “thinnest zone” with 20 plies of a quasi-isotropic lay-up [0/45/0/-45/0/45/0/-45/0/90]_s. Second on both sides, two “thicker zones” have respectively 36 plies with the lay-up [0/45/0/-45/0/45/0/-45/0/90/0/45/0/-45/0/45/0/-45]_s and 52 plies with the lay-up [(90/0/0/90/0/45/0/-45/0/45/0/-45/0/90/0/45/0/-45/0/45/0/-45/0/90/0/0)]_s. The drop-off zones are built with a 2.5 mm single latter step from the 11th ply to the 26th ply. This type of structure is representative

for the design singularities currently found in transportation.

All lay-up operations and embedding procedures are carried out manually in a gray-room, in order to preserve the electronic and optical characteristics of the embedded devices. Illustrations of these procedures are shown in Figure 2.

The temperature profile presented in Figure 3 is the temperature recorded by a thermocouple placed on the composite surface. The three main stages of the cure cycle are indicated.

The polymerization cycle begins at room temperature (25 °C) with a 2 °C/min heating slope up to 90 °C. At this temperature, a dwell step of 45 min is defined. After that, the temperature rises with the same 2 °C/min slope, to have a 120 °C dwell for 2 hrs. When the second plateau ends, the cooling phase is fixed with a -1 °C/min slope to get back at room temperature. From the beginning of the cycle until the end of the first temperature plateau, 2 bar of pressure is applied. The pressure is subsequently increased to 5 bar until the end of the polymerization cycle. During the entire autoclave cycle, a vacuum of 0.9 bar is maintained.

2.2 Multi-Instrumentation: flexible ultrasonic transducer (FUT)

FUT principle

The FUTs employed in this work are made of sol-gel sprayed piezoelectric composite films, and are able to work at high temperatures. The sol-gel sprayed film FUTs consist of a metal membrane, a piezoelectric composite film and a top electrode, as shown in Figure 4. The metal membrane can serve as bottom electrode, and the two electrodes define the active area of an FUT. Ultrasonic waves are generated by applying electric voltage across the two electrodes which sandwich the piezoelectric composite film, and then travel through successive layers of material and partially reflect on each interface. By receiving an electrical impulsion, the FUT produces an ultrasonic wave.

The parameters of the ultrasonic wave after travelling are unique and depend only on the atomic composition and the physical state of each material [6, 7]. FUTs have been designed as 4-mm diameter

piezoelectric elements working around a central frequency of 5 MHz.

Then, the stainless steel foil is cut in individual sensors of 12.7 mm length. The variations of the time of flight and amplitude of the echoes are related to the evolution of the viscoelastic properties of the material which are changing during the cure cycle, through phase transition and temperature.

To operate with the FUTs, some adjustments are performed on the metallic mold (cf. Figure 4). With the aim to well separate the ultrasonic echoes reflected from the 15 mm thick Al mold and the ones from the composite plate. As shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6, the thickness of the mold is increased. The position of the five FUTs target points are shown in Figure 7. 30 mm diameter holes were drilled into the mold to allow the insertion of steel rods with a 55 mm height, that are fixed with epoxy based glue.

In this way, for each pair of FUTs, one is glued below the rod and the other is placed on the top side of the mold in contact with the composite plate. The top FUT assemblies are surrounded by a silicone pyramid of $115 \times 55 \times 15 \text{ mm}^3$ (see Figure 4 and Figure 7). Such adaptation is conceived to leave a softer print on the composite plate when the pressure rises inside the autoclave.

During the entire polymerization cycle, the FUTs are stimulated producing different echoes which travel through the thickness of the composite plate. A multichannel acquisition system drives them alternatively in emission/reception or in reception. The bottom FUTs are working in pulse-echo mode, the top FUTs are only recording, and vice versa. In this work, only the echo signals, obtained by emitting with the FUTs on the mold's side (the **bottom FUTs**), are treated (cf. Figure 5). The signal received at the corresponding bottom FUT is simple to interpret and to process. On the top side, the 1 mm thick Teflon sheet cannot efficiently prevent the ultrasound energy from propagating to the FUT holder (6 mm thick Al plate), so that multiple echoes in the Al plate are recorded. The signals obtained in this configuration (emission by the **top FUTs**) are difficult to exploit for direct cure monitoring of composite and need further processing to complete the results exposed hereafter. The high acquisition rate of the emission-reception electronic system

allows to average the pulse-echo signal over 50 realizations, and to record several averaged signals per minute. This sampling rate is fast enough to ensure a good resolution of the evolving properties.

In the configuration shown in Figure 5, the echo labeled L_{m+c} generated by the bottom FUT, goes through the 55 mm steel rod and then through the composite sample, and is finally received by the top FUT. The echo labeled L_{m+3c} goes through the 55 mm steel rod and after a round trip in the composite, it is received by the top FUT. The amplitude of this echo is weak in most of the cases. The echo labeled L_{2m} goes through a 55 mm long steel rod, and is then reflected on the steel/composite interface, and will be received by the bottom FUT. The echo labeled L_{2m+2c} generated by bottom FUT, goes through a 55 mm long steel rod and composite, is reflected on the interface between the composite and the top FUT, and is finally received by the bottom FUT. This one is too weak and does not exceed the noise level and so it cannot be followed along the complete cure cycle (cf. Figure 6).

Only the echoes L_{m+c} and L_{2m} mentioned in Figure 5 can be easily detected all along the cycle and have been used for cure monitoring.

FUT sensor configuration

The assembly of flexible ultrasonic transducers (FUTs) mounted to monitor the polymerization through-the-thickness of the composite plate is shown in Figure 7.

As shown in Figure 7, a pair of FUTs is placed respectively, at the center of the thick zone consisting of 52 plies, at the center and 55 mm below the central line of the plate of the current zone (of 20 plies), at the thick zone of 36 plies (50 mm after the end of the drop-off) and finally, at the thick zone (50 mm before the end of the plate).

2.3 Multi-Instrumentation: fiber Bragg gratings

FBG principle

A Bragg grating (BG) is a periodic refractive index variation in the core of an optical fiber. When a broadband light spectrum is coupled into the fiber in which a Bragg grating is written, only a narrow part of the light spectrum will be back reflected (cf. Figure 8). The reflected spectrum is centred around

the Bragg-wavelength λ_B which is given by Equation 1:

$$\lambda_B = 2n_{eff}\Lambda \quad (1)$$

in which n_{eff} is the effective refractive index of the fiber at the position of the Bragg-grating, and Λ is the pitch of the Bragg-grating. Both parameters (n_{eff} , Λ) of the grating are strain and temperature dependent. The strain measurement principle is shown in Figure 8.

For most FBGs written in single-mode optical fibers, the centre strain approximation can be used to determine the theoretical strain response. Considering the optical and mechanical Eigen-axes of an optical fiber the following relations as function of strain can be written by Equation 2:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\Delta\lambda_{B,1'}}{\lambda_{B,1'}} &= \varepsilon_3' - \frac{1}{2}n_{eff,1'}^2[p_{11}\varepsilon_1' + p_{12}(\varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3')] \\ \frac{\Delta\lambda_{B,2'}}{\lambda_{B,2'}} &= \varepsilon_3' - \frac{1}{2}n_{eff,2'}^2[p_{11}\varepsilon_2' + p_{12}(\varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_3')] \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where ε_1' , ε_2' , ε_3' are the principal strain components along the axes of the fiber's coordinate system (cf. Figure 8). The sign ' is used to avoid confusion with the coordinate system corresponding to a single layer of a composite laminate. The strain components ε_4' , ε_5' and ε_6' are usually neglected in terms of the sensor response [8]. Further, in Equation (1), $\Delta\lambda_B$ is the Bragg peak wavelength shift, λ_B the initial mean Bragg peak wavelength, and p_{11} and p_{12} are the strain-optic coefficients. It is clear from Equation (1) that axial elongation ($\varepsilon_3' > 0$, $\varepsilon_1' = \varepsilon_2' = -\nu\varepsilon_3'$) or uniform compression ($\varepsilon_1' = \varepsilon_2' < 0$) will cause the Bragg peak reflection to shift homogeneously to higher or lower wavelengths.

However, an FBG embedded in a composite material will experience the complete strain field present in the composite material which makes it hard to distinguish between the transverse effects and the longitudinal effects occurring during complex loading situations and during the cure cycles.

Therefore, [4] have proposed to use an FBG which is embedded in a capillary to isolate the longitudinal strains during curing.

Capillary sensor

The principle of an FBG in a capillary is shown in Figure 9; in this way a situation of pure axial stress is established. In this case, the transverse strain components are directly related to the axial strain component via the Poisson's coefficient ($\varepsilon_1' = \varepsilon_2' = -\nu\varepsilon_3'$). By substituting this into Equation 2, the wavelength shifts in function of the axial strain are given by Equation 3:

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda_{B,2'}}{\lambda_{B,2'}} = \frac{\Delta\lambda_{B,1'}}{\lambda_{B,1'}} = \left[\left(1 - \frac{1}{2}n_{eff}^2 p_{12}\right) + \frac{1}{2}n_{eff}^2 \nu (p_{11} + p_{12}) \right] \varepsilon_3' \quad (3)$$

Note that before sealing the capillary, the optical fiber is pre-strained inside the capillary by more or less 1000 $\mu\varepsilon$. This enables the shielded FBG to measure compressive axial strain as well.

The above makes the read-out very simple in case of a thermal stable environment which is not the case with cure cycle monitoring applications. Therefore, one should think of a temperature compensation for the wavelength shifts measured by the capillary sensor. In this case this is easily done by using the read-out of the different thermocouples embedded in the sample nearby the capillary sensors. However note that for very large or thick composites a temperature variation could exist which does not facilitate the temperature compensation.

MOF sensor

By using FBGs written in particular MOFs, temperature compensation can become obsolete. Therefore this type of sensor is as well used in this study. The parameter measured to have this temperature invariance is called the birefringence or peak wavelength separation (cf. Equation 4):

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda_{B,1'}}{\lambda_{B,1'}} - \frac{\Delta\lambda_{B,2'}}{\lambda_{B,2'}} = -\frac{1}{2}n_{eff,1'}^2(p_{11} - p_{12})(\varepsilon_1' - \varepsilon_2') \quad (4)$$

This parameter is directly linked with strain variations solely occurring in the transverse direction of the fiber. This makes them complementary to the capillary sensor.

With this new technology (MOF), the evolution of peak separation for the embedded FBG is shown and it allows qualitative indications of the appearance of transverse strains from the beginning of the cooling stage until composite consolidation. These transverse strains are directly linked with the

appearance of residual stresses within and between the composite plies.

The cross-section of the MOF employed in this work and its initial spectrum are shown in Figure 10 [9].

The working of this MOF (Optical properties and strain calibration) is discussed more in detail by [10]. A cross sectional view of the embedded MOF is shown in Figure 11. The most sensitive direction of the MOF is oriented along the through the thickness direction of the material. It allows measuring very small strain differences during curing in the transverse direction.

FBG embedded sensor configuration

As discussed before DTG[®] (in a capillary) and MOF fiber Bragg gratings are used to monitor strain evolutions during curing as shown in Figure 12.

Three DTG[®]s sensors are placed respectively in the thick zone (DTG1), in the drop off (DTG2), and in the current zone (DTG3). All fibers are pre-tensioned in the capillaries. The distance between the different FBGs is 50 mm.

Two MOF FBGs are embedded; one in the middle of the current zone and one in the middle of the 52 plies thick zone (cf. Figure 12). All FBG sensors are embedded along the reinforcement fibers of their layer respectively. For the DTGs, this means that they are embedded in between two 0° layers. For the MOF, this is in between the two 90° layers of the symmetry plane.

3 Experimental results and discussion

3.1 FUT results

The time of flight and amplitude of the selected ultrasonic echoes are analyzed during the curing cycle. An example of a comparison of the evolution of these acoustic properties with the temperature measurement given by a thermocouple (called TC4) placed close to the studied zone is illustrated in Figure 13. The corresponding FUTs are operating on both sides of the 20 carbon-epoxy plies zone. The time of flight and the temperature have similar evolutions, in accordance with the autoclave settings. The variations of the time delay of the echoes traveling through the mold are used to correct the influence of temperature variations of the Al mold in the autoclave.

Figure 14 shows the evolutions of the time of flight and of the attenuation during the curing process. Five distinguishable phases are indicated with S_i ($i = 0$ to 4).

S_0 corresponds to the phase when the temperature increases from room temperature (RT) to a little above RT and when the resin becomes soft and the prepregs conform better to metal mold thanks to the increase of pressure. The time of flight through the prepregs decreases and more ultrasound energy goes through the prepregs (better coupling between sensors and composite part, and melting of interfaces between the prepregs). S_1 is the phase when temperature continues to increase up to 90 °C, the viscosity of the matrix decreases, and hence the sound velocity decreases and the time of delay increases. This delay increment is caused by a partial melting of the resin causing an irregularly impregnation of the fibers. At the beginning of this stage, ultrasonic attenuation in the composite increases with the temperature until reaching P_1 when matrix is melt, and then decreases with the temperature. S_2 relates to the phase when temperature is kept constant at 90 °C. The time of flight (ultrasound velocity) was expected to be nearly constant, but actually decreases because the viscosity of the matrix increases [11]. Such temperature plateau is used to ensure a homogenous melting of the composite and constant temperature does not mean that the material is at rest. More tests should be carried out, for example with only resin curing, to verify this phenomenon. S_3 is the phase when temperature increases from 90 °C to 120 °C and when the cure reaction happens. The attenuation reaches a maximum at the Gel Point, and then drops dramatically during the development of gelation. The last phase S_4 corresponds to the cooling down from 120 °C to RT, the time of flight decreases (sound velocity increases) together with the attenuation tending to final properties.

As Figure 14 shows, monitoring the time of flight and the attenuation of the echoes allows reliably inferring the initial state of composite plates during their manufacturing. FUTs are capable to acquire and to transmit qualitative information of the physical phenomena happening during the composite curing cycle.

The curing phases are identified with a unique signature beginning with the mold-composite

coupling, passing through resin reticulation and finishing with the composite consolidation. With these recognizable signatures, the feasibility of using FUTs to estimate the composite polymerization evolution is proven.

The different steps in the production process can be clearly plotted by FUTs; however it is also interested to have an accurate quantitative measure of the residual strain. Therefore, in this work we chose optical fibers as complementary instrumentation.

3.2 FBG results

Owing to the results obtained with the FUTs, we can distinguish two main phases in the curing cycle. The first stage is where the composite does not exist yet meaning that the optical fiber and the reinforcement fibers are not captured by the resin. In the second stage, the composite exists and we can follow up the residual strains which are built up in the composite material. In Figure 15, the results are shown of the measurements done with the MOF FBGs. The wavelength shifts of both peaks of the FBG are shown in red and black. The main driver of this shift is the temperature. However by analyzing Equation 4, we know that the peak separation (in green) is only driven by the strain induced in the sensor. Therefore, it gives a clear idea on when residual strains are built up e.g.; the onset of residual strain by chemical shrinkage corresponds with the measurements done with the FUTs. A peak separation is about 22 pm which corresponds to a macroscopic compressive transverse strain difference measured by the MOF of about $-130 \mu\epsilon$. It is shown that most of the residual strains in the transverse direction are induced during the cooling down phase of the cure cycle. This is essentially caused by the difference in thermal expansion coefficient between the matrix of the composite and the reinforcement fibers.

A different evolution of the wavelength shift (axial strains) is seen for the DTGs[®] surrounded with a capillary (cf. Figure 16). The measurements from the FUTs tell us that we should ignore the effects seen before the 125th minute of the cure cycle, since the composite does not exist. However, we should mention that the initiation of the polymerization phase is a grey zone in which the effects are difficult to explain. When analyzing the curves it is seen that all FBGs are loaded in compression. More or less

equal axial strains are measured by the three FBGs (about $-130 \mu\epsilon$). Differences can be caused by the different lay-ups at the position of the FBGs (thick, thin, drop-off zone) or can as well be caused by the variability which exists in the composite material (stacking uncertainty, fiber volume fraction ...). Note that all the measurements were temperature compensated using the temperature data of the thermocouple (called TC4) which is the closest to the different DTGs[®].

4 Conclusion

In this paper, we have addressed and demonstrated an added value of using embedded and more generally, complementary instrumentations. Beyond the difficulty involved by the autoclave environment, the challenge is to follow the physical state of composite parts during their forming process. Ultrasonic measurement using FUTs allow to follow clearly the different stages of the cycle. These measurements can be used to determine the point in the cure cycle at which strain transfer to the optical fiber sensor is plausible. During curing of thick composite parts or with changing lay-up, high temperature variations can exist in the material which makes it difficult to correct for temperature effects of the used sensors. At this stage of development, the mold properties variations with temperature have been corrected but the FUT efficiency has been shown. Ultrasonic sensor capabilities have not been fully exploited in real time. Monitoring of acquisition would be helpful, and the physical modeling of acoustic properties variations would allow quantifying the key parameters of physical constitutive law. Various sensor configurations can be designed, especially to record the birth of shear waves at gel point. Furthermore, instrumented mold is compatible with industrial production constrains.

Therefore, it is shown that the use of temperature independent parameters is essential. In this paper, we have shown that the peak separation or birefringence of a particular MOF FBG meets this requirement. Even the onset of the gelation and the corresponding transverse residual strains measured by the MOF FBG could be quantified.

Combined with the measurements of DTGs[®] embedded in capillaries to avoid the influence on the measurement of transverse residual strains a

complete overview of the induced residual strains can be obtained.

The main potential of being able to quantify the initial state (by measuring the induced residual strains) of a composite part is that a more reliable prediction of the service life could be provided in the future.

Fig.1. Schematic of the composite part made to monitor the cure cycle.

Fig.2. Double drop off evaluator (several stages during the lay-up phase).

Fig.3. Cure cycle used in this study.

Fig.4. Five pairs of FUTs and their adjustments to allow the operation for the studied CFRP part.

Fig.5. Signals generated by a bottom FUT.

Fig.6. Signals versus time with echoes obtained from configurations generated by a bottom FUT.

Fig.7. View of the location of the five pairs of FUTs on the studied CFRP part.

Fig.8. Strain measurement principle of a FBG.

Fig.9. FBG in a capillary shielded from transverse stress, principle (top) and during lay-up (bottom).

Fig.10. SEM of a MOF cross-section (left) and BG spectrum with the peak separation $\Delta\lambda$ (right).

Fig.11. Cross-section of the embedded MOF in the composite structure.

Fig.12. Optical Fiber network embedded in the studied CFRP part (capillaries in the thick zone (FBG1), in the drop off zone (FBG2), and in the thin zone (FBG3).

Fig.13. FUT signal (L_{2m} echo) and the temperature (Thermocouple TC4 in the current zone) versus time.

Fig.14. TOF and attenuation evolutions in the studied CFRP part with V value [Unitless],
 $L_{2m}TOF [ms] = 0.02 \cdot V + 19.2$,
 $TOF \text{ in composite } [ms] = 0.2 \cdot V + 2.2$,
 $attenuation [dB] = 4 \cdot V - 12$, $TC4 [^{\circ}C] = 10 \cdot V + 15$,
 $pressure = 0.45 \cdot V$.

Fig.15. Measurement curves (from MOF FBG and FUT) during the cure cycle of the composite part.

Fig.16. Strain shifts measured by the DTG[®] surrounded with no transverse strains effect thanks to capillaries with: in the thick zone (FBG1), in the drop off (FBG2), and in the thin zone (FBG3).

5 Acknowledgments

The authors would like to acknowledge the IWT-SBO Project “Self Sensing Composites - SSC” (contract no. 120024). The COST TD1001 action is acknowledged as well. The research project “Multi-sensor Instrumentation for Composite Materials and Structures (I2MC)” was financially supported by the Thematic Advanced Research Network for Aeronautic and Space Sciences & Technologies of Toulouse France (RTRA STAE) and the French SME Composites Expertise & Solutions

References

- [1] F. Collombet et al. Contribution of the embedded optical fiber with Bragg grating in composite structures for tests-simulations dialogue. *Mechanics of Adv. Materials and Structures*, 2006; 13, 429-439.
- [2] M. Kobayashi, C-K. Jen. Piezoelectric thick bismuth titanate/PZT composite film transducers for smart NDE of metals. *Smart Materials Structures* 2004; 13: pp. 951-956.
- [3] C. Sonnenfeld et al. Microstructured Optical Fiber Sensors Embedded in a Laminate Composite for Smart Material Applications. *Sensors*, 11, pp. 2566-2579; doi: 10.3390/s110302566, 2011.
- [4] G. Luyckx et al. Residual strain-induced birefringent FBGs for multi-axial strain monitoring of CFRP composite laminates. *NDT & E International*, 54 (0): pp.142-150, 2013.
- [5] C. Chojetzki et al. High-reflectivity draw-tower fiber Bragg gratings - arrays and single gratings of type II. *Optical Engineering*, 44(6): 060503, 2005.
- [6] M. Kobayashi et al. Flexible ultrasonic transducers. *IEEE Trans. Ultrason. Ferroelect. Freq. Contr.*, Vol. 53, pp.1478-1486, 2006.
- [7] M. Kobayashi, K.-T. Wu, et al. Structural Health Monitoring of Composites Using Integrated Ultrasonic Transducers. *Proc. of SPIE*, Vol. 6934, 693407-1, 2008.
- [8] D. Pinnow. *Elasto-optical materials*. In: Pressley RJ, editor. *Handbook of lasers*, 1971.
- [9] T. Geernaert et al. Bragg Grating Inscription in GeO₂-Doped Microstructured Optical Fibers, *J. Lightwave Tech.*, vol. 28, 10, pp. 1459–1467, 2010.
- [10] C. Sonnenfeld et al. Cure Cycle Monitoring of Laminated Carbon Fiber-Reinforced Plastic by Fiber Bragg Gratings in Micro-structured Optical Fiber, presented at the ICCM19, Montréal, Canada, 2013.
- [11] B.-C. Yoseph et al. Sensors for Cure monitoring of Composite Materials, *Review of Progress in Quantitative Nondestructive Evaluation*, pp. 1039-1046, 1993.